

Automatic Detection and Quantification of T-Wave Alternans

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Abstract

T-Wave Alternans (TWA) is considered to be an important indicator of risk of sudden cardiac death (SCD) and ventricular tachycardia (VT). In this work, fully automated method for TWA detection and quantification is presented. It includes: proper lead selection from multilead ECG signals and preprocessing for suppression of power-line interference, EMG noise and baseline drift but with accurate preservation of the T-wave. The T-wave and corresponding T-peak is separated from each ECG beat for further analysis using time-domain techniques. The presence of TWA is detected from a consistent beat to beat change in the amplitude of the T-wave. The TWA magnitude is obtained from the maximum variation between consecutive even and odd beats. Our algorithm is tested on a wide variety of test signals including 100 multilead ECG signals supplied by the PhysioNet/CINC Challenge 2008 authority. This approach results in a score of 0.911 in the scale of -1 to +1 which is also the best score among all participants.

1. Introduction

TWA was first described in 1908 by HE Hering; it is the variation in vector and amplitude of the T-wave that occurs on an every-other-beat basis [1]. There is some evidence that TWA is linked to alternations in cellular calcium homeostasis, which significantly influence the action potential duration (APD). It has been associated with an increased risk of SCD [2, 3] which accounts for 11% of all deaths and approximately 50% of all cardiovascular deaths [4]. In clinical applications, TWA analysis can be done as part of an exercise stress test as it is a rate-dependent phenomenon and microvolt TWA could develop in normal subjects at sufficiently high heart rate. An onset heart rate of less than 110 beats per minute is a conventional requisite for positivity as both TWA and false positive results increase with heart rate [5]. A positive TWA test is the presence of sustained alternans with a minimum amplitude of 1.9 μ V. Alternans should also be present for at

Figure 1. Visible TWA in ECG signal.

least 1 minute [6]. However, noise, premature beats, rapid changes in heart rate, or prominent beat-to-beat variability of RR intervals, failure to achieve target heart rate may all mask true alternans.

A variety of analysis methods have been proposed to automatically detect and estimate TWA in the ECG. These include both linear and nonlinear signal processing such as spectral analysis, complex demodulation, counting zero-crossings in a series of correlation coefficients, periodogram and complex demodulation analysis of T-wave principal components, Capon filtering, Poincaré maps, periodicity transforms, statistical tests, moving averages, maximum likelihood estimators and generalized likelihood ratio tests etc. [7]. The performance of such procedures depends on design parameters, which are usually not optimized, but selected from the designers experience.

Our algorithm consists of two basic parts: preprocessing and detection. The preprocessing part includes filtering and proper lead selection. The conditioned ECG signal is then processed for TWA detection. Simple peak detection algorithm has been used for separating the useful characteristic points. Further operations have been performed on the T-wave so that the detection and estimation part works successfully.

2. TWA Challenge Database

The challenge database has been assembled from a wide variety of sources [8]. It contains 100 multichannel ECG

records sampled at 500 Hz with 16 bit resolution over a 32 mV range. The subjects include patients with myocardial infarctions, transient ischemia, ventricular tachyarrhythmias, and other risk factors for sudden cardiac death, as well as healthy controls and synthetic cases with calibrated amounts of T-wave alternans. In most cases, each record contains the standard 12 diagnostic ECG signals, but a few contain only 2 or 3 signals.

3. TWA Detection Method

The TWA detection algorithm comprises three stages: preprocessing, data reduction and the TWA analysis, which can be further decomposed into the detection and estimation substages. The scheme is represented in Fig. 1. The input to the system is the digitized ECG signal. The possible outputs include the decision whether TWA is present or absent, and the TWA amplitude if it is present.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the TWA detection algorithm.

3.1. Lead Selection

T-wave represents the repolarization of the ventricles. As the TWA magnitude is in the range of microvolts, proper lead selection is an important part to detect its presence in the signal. In a standard ECG lead system lead I, aVF, V_2 and V_3 shows 100% specificity [9]. Bipolar limb lead-I and chest lead V_3 are selected for 2 or 3 and 12 lead ECG signals respectively as they contain the highest amplitude of T-wave in each cases. In some special cases lead-II and V_2 might also be taken into considerations due to physical positioning of the heart or misplacement of leads.

Figure 3. (a) Lead-I and (b) V_3 ECG signals.

3.2. Filtering

Filtering is a must for ECG signal processing as it is prone to various kinds of noise and interference. Yet, extra care is needed as important properties might be eliminated during filtration process. A soft bandpass filter (0.5Hz to 50Hz) is used in this process to preserve the T-wave in particular.

Figure 4. (a) Noisy and (b) filtered ECG signals.

Figure 5. R and T peaks detection from (a) Lead I and (b) V_3 .

3.3. Peak Detection

In order to find the T-wave and corresponding peaks, the local maximum value in each ECG beat is detected. Normally R is the highest peak in an ECG beat of lead-I or II. But, in case of V_2 and V_3 , the T-peak might also be the local peak. At first these local peaks are temporarily termed as R. Afterwards the next highest peak of an ECG beat is detected. The final decisions about R and T-peaks are taken from the relative distance between them. An R-peak is followed by the ST segment and T-wave. As the distance between R and T is much smaller than that between T and next R, it becomes easier to separate them from relative distance rather than from variable amplitude levels in different leads.

3.4. TWA Detection and Quantification

After separating the T-waves successfully, the even and odd T-peaks are separated in two groups. The difference between these matrices decide whether it would be termed as a TWA or not [10]. If the difference values tend to gather closely around some particular value with limited number of zero crossings then TWA is assumed to be present. Fur-

ther verification is done from the Heart rate, degree and duration of variation among the even and odd T-peaks. The maximum difference value is termed as the alternan magnitude according to the PhysioNet/CINC 2008 challenge announcement [8]. In order to avoid the effects of filtering, the extreme end-values were excluded from calculation.

Figure 6. TWA (a) Detection and (b) Quantification.

4. Results

The quality parameters for this algorithm are given in Table 1. They are obtained by comparing the TWA/no TWA decisions suggested by the algorithm with the decisions suggested by the PhysioNet/CINC Challenge 2008. The accuracy of this detection method is 98%. The definition of the quality parameters [11] are given as below.

Sensitivity is the ability (probability) to detect TWA. It is given by the quotient

$$\frac{\text{detected cases of "TWA"}}{\text{all cases of "TWA"}} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (1)$$

where TP being the number of true positive decisions, FN the number of false negative decisions.

Specificity is the probability to identify "no TWA" correctly. It is given by the quotient

$$\frac{\text{detected cases of "noTWA"}}{\text{all cases of "noTWA"}} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad (2)$$

where TN is the number of true negative decisions, and FP is the number of false positive decisions.

Positive predictivity is defined by

$$\frac{\text{detected cases of "TWA"}}{\text{all cases classified by the algorithm as "TWA"}} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3)$$

Positive predictivity is the probability, that classified TWA as truly TWA.

Accuracy is defined by

$$\frac{\text{all true decisions}}{\text{all decisions}} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN} \quad (4)$$

Accuracy is the probability to obtain a correct decision.

Table 1. Performance of the TWA detection algorithm

Quality Parameter	TWA
Sensitivity (%)	96.67
Specificity (%)	98.57
Positive Predictivity (%)	96.67
Accuracy (%)	98

The false negative and false positive results occur mostly due to excessive noise in the test signal or very low amplitude of TWA ($2\mu V$ in this case). Out of 30 ECG signals with synthesized TWA our algorithm successfully detected 29 of them. The alternan magnitude was also quite satisfactory as it achieved the top-score 0.911 where the next top-scores are: 0.890 and 0.881.

5. Discussion and conclusions

A novel method for detecting and quantifying TWA has been presented in this paper. The detection is approached by a simple time domain technique following the TWA definition whereas most methods are based on the short-time Fourier transform of the beat-to-beat series. This technique considers that proper lead selection and filtering are very important as the magnitude of TWA varies a lot from lead to lead. Improper filtering might also hide low-amplitude TWA. It has been demonstrated that the proposed method is able to detect TWA with the highest accuracy for the Challenge database. The TWA quantification results are also good and further improvement can be achieved by incorporating multilead ECG signal analysis. The automatic algorithm proposed here has strong potential to be applied in clinical applications for faster and accurate detection and quantification of TWA.

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